

DETERMINATION OF PLASTIC LIMIT USING MATHEMATICAL MODEL

Gerald Maregesi

Email: gerald.maregesi@aesi.co.tz

ABSTRACT

*Using a mathematical model which predicts the moisture-penetration relationship up to zero moisture content, a model which computes the plastic limit based on the penetration value at the plastic limit is proposed. The model was developed using 194 Atterberg limit test results and validated using 44 soil data collected from the literature. Calculated and determined plastic limits agreed within the narrow range of $PL \pm 3$, with 92% of the results within the accuracy of $PL \pm 1$. The calculated plastic limit using the proposed model was found to be within the statistical testing bound of $PL \pm PL * 18\%$ provided in AASHTO T90-94.*

INTRODUCTION

The procedure of plastic limit determination is very subjective and error-prone. In order to improve the accuracy and repeatability of the test results, several researchers have suggested extrapolating the plastic limit from the cone penetrometer flow curve. Towner (1973), Harison (1988), and Feng (2002) proposed that the moisture content corresponding to 2 mm of British fall cone penetration represents the plastic limit of the soil. Nevertheless, practical limitations make it difficult or impossible to achieve a penetration of less than 3 mm such that the plastic limit can be directly determined from the fall cone flow curve. As a result, many researchers have proposed extrapolation methods. Little has been done to develop a mathematical model that can be used to predict the moisture-penetration relationship at a lower penetration value of less than 3 mm. Maregesi (2022) proposed a sigmoidal mathematical model which predicts the moisture-penetration values up to the lowest moisture content, at which, due to practical limitation is impossible to determine the British fall cone penetration of the soil.

This paper presents a mathematical model that can be used to compute the plastic limit of the soil using

the penetration value at the plastic limit calculated using the fall cone flow curve mathematical model (Maregesi, 2022). The proposed model of computing the plastic limit was found to estimate the plastic limit within the statistical testing bound of the plastic limit provided in AASHTO T90-94. The accuracy of the proposed model is within $PL \pm 3$, with 92% of the results within the accuracy of $PL \pm 1$. This study indicates that penetration at plastic limit varies widely, and no single British fall cone penetration value that defines the plastic limit of soil.

THE FALL CONE LIQUID LIMIT FLOW CURVE

The British fall cone moisture-penetration relationship can be fitted using equation 1 [Maregesi (2022)]. This equation fits the moisture-penetration relationship for soil tested within the 3-25 mm penetration range. Further, with this equation, it is possible to predict soil penetration values at a low moisture content with a penetration value of less than 3 mm, at which practical limitations make it impossible to determine the penetration values of soil. The typically fitted fall cone moisture penetration curve (25-5 mm penetration values) and predicted penetration values (5-0 mm penetration values) is shown in Figure 1.

$$h = \frac{40}{1 + \left(\frac{x}{LL}\right)^{-(0.1 LL m)}} \dots \dots (1)$$

Where,

'h' is the penetration depth at any moisture content, 'x' is the moisture content, 'LL' is the liquid limit, and 'm' is the slope of the flow curve computed using equation 2.

$$m = \frac{25 - 5}{w_{25} - w_5} = \frac{20}{w_{25} - w_5} \dots \dots (2)$$

where

W_{25} and W_5 are water contents corresponding to 25 mm and 5 mm penetration values, respectively.

Figure 1: The fall cone data points fitted using equation 1

DEVELOPMENT OF A MODEL FOR COMPUTING PLASTIC LIMIT

Soils with a wide range of liquid limits, plastic limits, and plasticity index were used to develop the mathematical model of computing the plastic limit. The liquid limit ranged from 16 to 202, the plastic limit ranged from 9 to 108, and the plasticity index ranged from 3 to 170. The box plot in Figure 2 shows the summary and the distribution of the Atterberg limit data used for developing the mathematical model.

The penetrations at the plastic limit for 194 soils tested during this study were computed using equation 1 (by substituting the moisture content 'x' with a moisture content corresponding to the plastic limit) and were found to be in the range of 0.18 mm to 3.47 mm with an average penetration of 1.54 mm, which is closer to 2 mm penetration value advocated by several researchers as the penetration of the soil at the plastic limit [Towner (1973), Harison (1988), Feng(2002)]. The histogram showing the fall cone penetration of the soil at the plastic limit is shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that 68% of the penetrations values at the plastic limit are within the range of 0.80-2.3 mm. The fall cone penetration at the plastic limit is within a narrow range, leading many researchers to

suggest that one value of fall cone penetration can be used to define the soil's plastic limit. [Feng (2002), Muntohar & Hashim (2005), Maregesi (2022)].

Figure 2: The summary of the Atterberg limit data used for the development of the mathematical model of computing plastic limit

Figure 3: Histogram showing the penetration at plastic limit

Figure 4 shows the relationship between fall cone penetration at the plastic limit and the slope of the flow curve, plastic limit, liquid limit, and plasticity index. It can be seen that a single fall cone penetration value cannot be used to define the plastic limit of soil because the penetration at the plastic limit is very variable. Despite the poor correlation between penetration at the plastic limit and slope, liquid limit, plastic limit, and plasticity index, the best fit curve fitted using the loss

regression model indicates that as the flow curve slope increases, the penetration at the plastic limit increases. However, as the liquid limit or plasticity index increases, the penetration at the plastic limit decreases. There is no observed trend between the plastic limit and penetration at the plastic limit because most penetration values are normally distributed in close proximity to the mean penetration value.

Figure 4: variation of penetration at the plastic limit with (a) Fall cone slope, (b) liquid limit, (c) plastic limit, (d) plasticity index (best-fit curve fitted using the loess regression model)

Analysis of the test results revealed that the penetration at the plastic limit is highly correlated to the flow curve constant 'n' value as defined in equation 3. The relationship between the flow curve constant 'n' value and penetration at the plastic limit fitted with a double-term exponential function is shown in Figure 5 ($R^2=0.9916$). The fitted equation is given as equation 4.

$$n = 0.1 m LL \dots \dots (3)$$

$$h_{PL} = 3.884 - 4.835e^{-0.2535n} - 1.289e^{-0.003797n} \dots (4)$$

Equation 3 can be substituted into equation 4, resulting in equation 5.

$$h_{PL} = 3.884 - 4.835e^{-0.02535 m LL} - 1.289e^{-0.0003797 m LL} \dots (5)$$

Where,

' h_{PL} ' is the penetration at the plastic limit, 'm' is the flow curve slope as defined by equation 2, 'LL' is the liquid limit

Figure 5: The relationship between the n-value (flow constant) and the penetration at the plastic limit ($R^2=0.9916$).

Therefore, the soil penetration at the plastic limit generally depends on the interactions of two parameters, namely the liquid limit and the slope of the fall cone flow curve. Equation 4 suggest that the maximum penetration at the plastic limit for all type of soil computed using this proposed mathematical model is 3.884 mm (as the value of 'n' tends to infinity, the penetration at the plastic limit converges to a maximum penetration value of 3.884 mm). The contour plot of equation 5 showing the relationship between the slope, liquid limit, and penetration at the plastic limit is shown in figure 6. It can be seen that the soil at the plastic limit can take any value of the penetration depending on the slope of the fall cone, suggesting that a single value of fall cone penetration cannot be used to define the plastic limit of the soil. Furthermore, it can be

seen that soils with a fall cone slope of less than 0.8 are sensitive to changes in slope, as evidenced by closely spaced penetration contour values.

Figure 6: Contour plot showing the relationship between the penetration at the plastic limit, liquid limit, and slope of the fall cone flow curve

COMPUTATION OF SOIL PLASTIC LIMIT USING MATHEMATICAL MODEL

The plastic limits of 194 soils tested during this investigation were computed using equation 6. Equation 6 is derived from equation 1 by making the moisture content 'x' a subject and replacing it with moisture content corresponding to the plastic limit of the soil. The contour plot of equation 6 showing the variation of the slope, liquid limit, and plastic limit is shown in Figure 7. For a slope of less than 0.8, the plastic limit is highly sensitive to changes in the fall cone slope, as evidenced by closely spaced contour values. The sensitivity of the plastic limit with change in slope values decreases as the fall cone slope increases and becomes almost insensitive to slope variation when the slope of the fall cone is more than 3. The comparison between the determined and the computed plastic limit is shown in Figure 8. It can be seen that the calculated and the determined plastic limit are in close agreement and well within the statistical testing bound of the plastic limit, which in accordance with AASHTO T90-94 is supposed to be within the accuracy of $PL \pm PL * 18\%$. The residual analysis of the fitted plastic limit data is shown in Figure 9, from which it can be seen that the model's accuracy is within the range of $PL \pm 3$. The residual histogram (Figure 10) indicates that 92% of the results are within the accuracy of $PL \pm 1$.

$$PL = \left(\frac{40}{\frac{h_{PL}}{LL \cdot 0.1LLm}} - 1 \right)^{-\frac{10}{LLm}} \dots (6)$$

Figure 7: Contour plot showing the relationship between the slope of the fall cone, liquid limit, and plastic limit

Figure 8: Comparison between measured and computed plastic limits (194 soil samples)

Figure 9: Difference between the measured, computed plastic limits (194 soil samples)

Figure 10: Residual histogram

VALIDATION OF THE MODEL USING DATA FROM THE LITERATURE

Feng (2001, 2004) presented the liquid and plastic limits data for 30 soils (in 2001) and 21 soils (in 2004). The fall cone flow curve data were fitted using a linear log-log model in the form of

$$\log w = \log c + m \log d \dots (7)$$

Where 'w' is the water content, 'c' is the water content at d=1 mm, 'm' is the slope of the flow curve, and 'd' is the penetration depth. The fall cone flow curves for all 51 soil samples were generated and transformed into a linear model in the form shown in equation (8).

$$y = m_1x + c \dots (8)$$

Where,

m_1 is the slope of the flow curve computed using equation 2.

Out of the 51 test results, 44 were used in the validation of the model. 7 test results were omitted in the model validation because its calculated liquid limit using the flow-curve parameters, namely 'm' and 'c', was inconsistent with the reported liquid limit. The summary of the data used to validate the model is shown in the appendix. The comparison between the calculated and the determined plastic limit for 44 soils used for the validation of the model is shown in Figure 11, from which it can be seen that the calculated plastic limit is in very close agreement with the determined plastic limit and are within the statistical testing bound of $PL \pm PL * 18\%$. The accuracy of the model was found to be $PL \pm 4$ except for one result, which its accuracy was found to be $PL - 6$. The residual analysis plot is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 11: Comparison between determined and computed plastic limit

Figure 12: Residual analysis plot

CONCLUSION

The penetration at the plastic limit is very variable and depends on the interaction between the liquid limit and the slope of the fall cone flow curve; thus, the plastic limit of the soil cannot be defined using one unique penetration value.

The proposed mathematical model calculates the plastic limit within the statistical bound of determining the plastic limit, which in accordance with AASHTO T90-94, is $PL \pm PL * 18\%$. The use of the proposed model for determining the plastic implies that both liquid and plastic limits can be determined using the fall cone penetration test with exceptional that instead of establishing the moisture penetration relationship within the usual penetration range of 20 ± 5 mm, the moisture penetration relationship is supposed to be established within the penetration range of 3-25 mm, with 5 mm penetration being the absolute minimum.

References:

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		Data and parameters as Reported in Feng 2002 and 2004 (log w=log c+m log d)						Data and parameters computed during this study (y=m ₁ x+c)							
No		Slope (m)	Intercept [c]	LL	LL Computed	PL	m ₁	PI	Pen at PL	Pen at PL computed	LL Computed Using parameter m & C	Difference between Reported and calculated LL	PL Deter	PL computed	Residual
1	Kaolin B	0.421	19	72	66.9	26	0.5602		0.86	1.04	66.94	5.06	26.00	29.33	-3.33
2	Taipei clay	0.332	15	41	40.6	21	1.1258		1.82	1.30	40.60	0.40	21.00	19.66	1.34
3	Taipei clay	0.292	15	36	36.0	18	1.4148		1.14	1.49	36.00	0.00	18.00	19.01	-1.01
4	Taipei clay	0.252	17	36	36.2	22	1.5982	Feng 2001	2.16	1.72	36.20	-0.20	22.00	20.99	1.01
5	Sinjun Clay	0.322	14	36	36.7	19	1.2752		1.86	1.29	36.70	-0.70	19.00	17.16	1.84
6	Taipei clay	0.322	17	43	44.6	24	1.0502		2.30	1.26	44.60	-1.60	24.00	20.13	3.87
7	Panama clay (Feng 2002)	0.321	47	125	123.0	60	0.382		1.26	1.37	123.00	2.00	60.00	62.07	-2.07
8	Kaolin A	0.301	20	50	49.3	25	1.0064		1.27	1.47	49.30	0.70	25.00	26.11	-1.11
9	bentonite	1.000	17	423	340.0	37	0.0588	Feng 2000	0.16	0.16	340.00	83.00	37.00	45.73	-8.73
10	Shellhaven clay	0.436	26	97	96.0	32	0.3811		0.68	0.87	96.00	1.00	32.00	34.68	-2.68
11	London clay	0.410	21	73	71.7	25	0.5358		0.64	0.98	71.70	1.30	25.00	28.47	-3.47
12	Horten Clay	0.266	13	30	28.8	16	1.9148	Skempton and Northey	1.32	1.72	28.80	1.20	16.00	17.48	-1.48
13	Gosport clay	0.352	28	80	80.4	30	0.5417		0.55	1.18	80.40	-0.40	30.00	35.72	-5.72
14	Swedish clay	0.425	26	83	92.9	31	0.402		1.00	0.68	92.90	-9.90	31.00	24.61	6.39
15	Swedish clay	0.360	25	70	73.5	28	0.5814		0.77	1.06	73.50	-3.50	28.00	28.86	-0.86
16	Swedish clay	0.360	22	63	64.7	23	0.6607		0.53	1.10	64.70	-1.70	23.00	26.76	-3.76
17	Swedish clay	0.308	21	53	52.8	24	0.9218	Karlson 1961	0.83	1.41	52.80	0.20	24.00	26.92	-2.92
18	Drammen clay	0.350	12	35	34.2	20	1.2776		3.33	1.24	34.20	0.80	20.00	16.21	3.79
19	kaolini	0.343	21	59	58.7	33	0.9816		1.37	1.73	58.70	0.30	33.00	34.57	-1.57
20	Gaulty clay	0.345	23	65	64.7	29	0.6848	Wood (1985)	1.09	1.23	64.70	0.30	29.00	29.94	-0.94
21	bentonite	1.000	16	526	320.0	38	0.0625		0.04	0.65	320.00	206.00	38.00	151.21	-113.21
22	Turkey soil	0.569	20	110	109.9	27	0.2705		0.60	0.47	109.90	0.10	27.00	24.81	2.19
23	Turkey soil	0.335	21	52	57.2	22	0.792		0.77	1.08	57.20	-5.20	22.00	21.78	0.22
24	bandung clay	0.312	39	100	99.3	49	0.4851		1.26	1.40	99.30	0.70	49.00	50.44	-1.44
25	bandung clay	0.341	31	86	86.1	39	0.5192		1.13	1.24	86.10	-0.10	39.00	39.76	-0.76
26	bandung clay	0.318	30	78	77.8	37	0.6095		1.14	1.36	77.80	0.20	37.00	38.56	-1.56
27	bandung clay	0.292	30	72	71.9	37	0.7084		1.31	1.49	71.90	0.10	37.00	38.07	-1.07
28	bandung clay	0.237	32	65	65.1	38	0.9384		1.45	1.83	65.10	-0.10	38.00	39.50	-1.50
29	bandung clay	0.239	30	63	61.4	38	0.9877		1.92	1.86	61.40	1.60	38.00	38.79	-0.79
30	bandung clay	0.216	31	59	59.2	38	1.1197	Harrison (1988)	2.03	1.97	59.20	-0.20	38.00	37.70	0.30
31	bentonite (B)	1.148	14	458	436.0	31	0.0419		0.25	-0.25	436.00	22.00	31.00		
32	ca-Montmorillonite	0.522	36	192	172.0	52	0.1847		0.57	0.80	172.00	20.00	52.00	63.96	-11.96
33	Illite	0.282	18	43	41.9	22	1.2534		1.20	1.60	41.90	1.10	22.00	23.84	-1.84
34	Kaolin (K)	0.362	22	70	65.1	28	0.6538		0.82	1.28	65.10	4.90	28.00	33.26	-5.26
35	50% B+50% K	0.770	17	182	170.0	29	0.1399		0.44	0.20	170.00	12.00	29.00	22.64	6.36
36	10% B +90% K	0.472	18	89	74.0	25	0.4641		0.45	1.09	74.00	15.00	25.00	37.42	-12.42
37	Taipei clay (1)	0.282	35	85	81.5	43	0.6446		1.17	1.63	81.50	3.50	43.00	47.75	-4.75
38	Taipei clay (2)	0.274	22	51	49.7	27	1.0901		1.30	1.66	49.70	1.30	27.00	28.98	-1.98
39	Taipei clay (3)	0.299	23	56	56.3	28	0.8867		1.21	1.44	56.30	-0.30	28.00	28.89	-0.89
40	Taipei clay (4)	0.356	25	74	72.6	32	0.5939		1.06	1.21	72.60	1.40	32.00	33.59	-1.59
41	Taipei clay (5)	0.227	21	40	41.5	25	1.5305		1.72	1.83	41.50	-1.50	25.00	24.36	0.64
42	Taipei clay (6)	0.176	25	43	42.3	28	1.8814		1.37	2.31	42.30	0.70	28.00	30.45	-2.45
43	Taipei clay (7)	0.223	20	38	39.0	23	1.6522		1.40	1.88	39.00	-1.00	23.00	23.53	-0.53
44	Taipei clay (8)	0.258	15	33	32.5	18	1.7454		1.29	1.72	32.50	0.50	18.00	19.26	-1.26
45	Taipei clay (9)	0.393	17	56	55.2	22	0.7208		0.95	1.04	55.20	0.80	22.00	22.83	-0.83
46	Taipei clay (10)	0.284	24	53	56.2	29	0.9288		1.48	1.42	56.20	-3.20	29.00	27.12	1.88
47	Taipei clay (11)	0.184	22	39	38.2	25	2.005		1.40	2.26	38.20	0.80	25.00	27.21	-2.21
48	Taipei clay (12)	0.249	20	43	42.2	24	1.3871		1.33	1.79	42.20	0.80	24.00	25.73	-1.73
49	Taoyuan clay	0.295	19	48	46.0	23	1.0988		1.01	1.56	46.00	2.00	23.00	26.13	-3.13
50	Pintong Silt	0.174	12	20	20.2	14	3.9843		2.04	2.29	20.20	-0.20	14.00	14.07	-0.07
51	Panama clay	0.314	24	64	61.5	30	0.7639	Feng (2004)	1.16	1.41	61.50	2.50	30.00	32.53	-2.53